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Physics Student Teachers Experience On Teaching Practice, In Port Harcourt City Metropolis Of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated Physics Student Teachers' Experience during Teaching Practice, in Port Harcourt city Metropolis of Rivers State. The study focused on Students enrolled in Undergraduate Programs in the University of Port Harcourt who had participated in at least one Teaching Practice exercise, most preferably the last one of the 2022/2023 session. To conduct this test, a sample size of 20 respondents were drawn from a population of 20 Physics Student Teachers using census sampling technique. A Questionnaire was used in retrieving information from the respondents. The reliability coefficient of the instrument is $r = 0.85$ using cronbach alpha. This instrument answered 2 research questions and tested one hypothesis. From the responses gotten, the findings shown that the Physics Student Teachers had a lot of positive experiences from the teaching practice exercise, however, there was a slight difference in the response of the male and female towards the experiences gained. It was therefore recommended that the teaching Practice exercise should be made compulsory for the Physics student teachers and should be carried out twice before graduation, strict supervision should be done in the process.

Keywords: Physics Student, Teaching Practice,

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a process that involves two or more people: a teacher and a learner. Smith (2020) defined teaching as the process of attending to people's needs, experiences and feelings so that they learn things, and go beyond what is given. Teaching practice, a practical component of teacher education, offers trainees the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in real classroom settings. During this period, aspiring educators are placed in institutions such as schools or colleges under the guidance of experienced mentors. Steadman (2018) defined teaching practice as a student teacher's time spent in a school as part of their training, where they teach under supervision. Teaching practice is indispensable as it equips trainees with practical teaching and classroom management skills, providing valuable experience not attainable through mere observation or trial and error. In Nigeria, teaching practice is a compulsory course for all aspiring teachers, contributing significantly to the nation's educational goals (Bruinsma and Jansen, 2010). The National Commission for Colleges of Education outlines clear objectives for teaching practice (NCCE, 2012).

The study of Physics enables students to understand the fundamental and natural laws that govern the universe. However, learning Physics is not only about memorizing formulas and solving equations. It also requires developing a scientific mindset and a curiosity to explore the physical world. This is where teaching practice comes in. Teaching practice can provide Physics teachers with the opportunity to design and implement engaging and meaningful lessons that spark students' interest and curiosity in Physics.

Teaching practice is an integral component of teacher education that provides student teachers with the opportunity to apply their theoretical knowledge and skills in real classroom settings. It also exposes them to the challenges and realities of the teaching profession, such as curriculum implementation, classroom management, learner diversity, assessment and feedback, and professional development. Teaching practice is therefore essential for preparing student teachers for their future roles and responsibilities as teachers. Yan and He (2015) argue that teaching practice is essential for developing teachers' professional competence and identity, as well as for enhancing students' learning outcomes and motivation. They claim that teaching practice provides opportunities for teachers to apply their theoretical knowledge, reflect on their actions, receive feedback, and collaborate with peers and mentors.

Effective Physics education places a strong emphasis on equipping educators with the ability to teach both theory and practical science skills. These practical skills development involves organizing practical activities and the laboratory activities are instrumental in developing these skills (Handayani, Yuwono, & Taufik, 2015). Amankwah, Oti-Agyen, & Sam (2017) define Physics Student Teachers as individuals actively engaged in professional teacher training within colleges or universities. The impact of their teaching practice extends far beyond personal development, influencing the academic prospects of future generations. Teaching practice is not merely a prerequisite for obtaining a teaching degree;

The experiences gained during this phase are instrumental in shaping the confidence, effectiveness, and professional growth of aspiring educators. The experiences of physics student teachers during teaching practice ranges from classroom experience where teaching practice stands as a pivotal component of teacher education, immersing Physics student teachers in the authentic dynamics of classroom environments is very rewarding. (Nkambule & Mukeredzi, 2017). This immersion allows Physics Student Teachers to assume the role of actual educators, providing them with a first hand experience of the challenges and rewards associated with teaching.

The classroom experience during teaching practice may raise doubts among Physics student teachers about their ability to navigate unfamiliar situations and effectively engage with students (Perry, 2004). The hands-on nature of teaching practice allows student teachers to confront and overcome obstacles, fostering resilience and adaptability in the face of real-world teaching scenarios which also involving hands on activities. (Msangya, Mkoma & Yihuan, 2016). The experiences gained during teaching practice play a pivotal role in shaping the confidence and effectiveness of Physics Student Teachers in their future roles (Oyedeki & Oke, 2020). This bridge between theory and practice is essential for preparing aspiring educators for the dynamic and multifaceted nature of the teaching profession.

During teaching practice exercise the supervisors played a pivotal role in ensuring that student teachers received constructive feedback, personalized guidance, and the necessary resources to navigate the intricate landscape of teaching practice. (Mutseekwa and Mushoriwa, 2021). Again, the student teacher sees the school environment as their future workplace. Teaching practice extends beyond the classroom, fostering professional growth and networking opportunities for Physics Student Teachers (Nghia & Tai, 2019). The cooperative relationship with experienced educators contributes to the on going mentorship and support.

Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) theory was used for the study. To this theory, effective learning occurs when all four stages of the learning cycle are engaged, creating a continuous and adaptive learning process was adopted for the study (Kolb, 1984). This involves the Pre-service Physics teachers to process their experiences, translate them into theoretical knowledge and pedagogical strategies, which can be applied in future teaching contexts.

Bada and Jita (2023) investigated the experiences of pre-service Physics teachers during Teaching Practice. Findings from their study revealed that secondary schools have qualified Physics teachers who

have good mastery of the subject matter. The findings of the study revealed that the experience pre-service teachers have during teaching practice exercises has the capacity to determine how far they would go in the chosen profession.

Another study by Mafugu (2022) worked on science pre-service teachers' experience with mentors during teaching practice. The results indicate that although most preservice teachers received the necessary guidance in theory and practical lessons as well as assessment, a significant proportion of the participants were not assisted adequately during the exercise.

Çebi and Reisoğlu (2020) undertook a study on Digital Competence, which sought the Perspective of Pre-service Teachers in Turkey and to determine whether these opinions vary according to gender, branch and perceived level of digital competence. A cross-sectional survey model was used and the study was conducted with 518 pre-service teachers who were studying in different provinces of Turkey. The study used a digital competence questionnaire as a data collection tool. One major finding that stood out was the difference in different digital competency areas which affects teaching practice. The male pre-service teachers were better at information and data literacy, digital content creation, safety, and problem-solving while the females were better at communication and collaboration during the Teaching Practice period.

Statement of the Problem

Teaching practice is an integral component of teacher education, essential for shaping the pedagogical skills and professional identities of pre-service Physics teachers. Anxiety and stress can loom over these aspiring teachers, stemming from concerns related to classroom management, content knowledge, pedagogical skills, and students' engagement. Moreover, low motivation and confidence levels may persist due to inadequate supervision, feedback, syllabus overload and support from mentors and peers. Do teachers on teaching practice have any experience during teaching practice? Therefore, this study out to investigate the experiences gained by the Physics students teachers during the teaching practice programme.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate Physics teachers' experience on teaching practice, in Port Harcourt. Specifically, the following objectives guided the following objectives:

1. To examine the experiences of Physics student teachers during their teaching practice exercise.
2. To examine the experiences of Physics student teachers during their teaching practice with respect to gender.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the experiences of Physics student teachers during their teaching practice exercise?
2. What is the experiences of Physics student teachers during their teaching practice with respect to gender?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference between the experiences of the male and female students teachers during the teaching exercise.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey research design and focuses on the experiences of Physics student teachers engaged in teaching practice during the 2022/2023 academic session at the University of Port Harcourt.

The population is same as sample size of this study which comprised of all 20 Physics student teachers who are currently enrolled in Education undergraduate programs in the Department of Curriculum Studies and Educational Technology at the University of Port Harcourt and actively engaged in teaching practice during the 2022/23 academic session. The instrument for the study is a structured questionnaire, named "Physics Student Teachers' Experience on Teaching Practice Questionnaire" (PSTETP), designed to capture quantitative insights into the experiences of Physics student teachers. The instrument was

validated. The reliability of the questionnaire was evaluated using Pearson Product Moment coefficient $r = 0.62$. The collected data were analysed using mean and standard deviation while the hypothesis was tested with t test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research question 1: *What are the experiences of Physics student teachers during their teaching practice exercise?*

Table 1: Experiences of Physics Student Teachers during Teaching Practice

S/N	QUESTION	SA	A	D	SD	TOTAL WEIGHT	WEIGHTED MEAN	Decision
1	I learnt how to prepare a lesson note effectively during the Teaching Practice	40	18	8	0	66	3.3	Agreed
2	I got a constructive feedback during the teaching practice exercise	16	36	12	0	64	3.2	Agreed
3	I was able to overcome stage fright during teaching.	24	36	4	0	64	3.2	Agreed
4	The teaching resources available during my practice were not adequate.	8	30	16	0	54	2.7	Agreed
5	I encountered positive interactions with the students during my teaching practice.	16	18	8	0	60	3.0	Agreed
6	I faced challenges in maintaining classroom discipline in the course of the teaching practice exercise.	32	24	8	0	64	3.2	Agreed
7	The support from mentor teachers positively influenced my teaching practice.	40	18	8	0	66	3.3	Agreed
8	It was not easy to adapt my teaching methods to suit different learning styles.	16	30	12	0	29	2.9	Agreed
9	I believe my teaching practice helped me develop effective communication skills.	40	18	8	0	66	3.3	Agreed
10	The overall teaching practice experience was rewarding to me	40	12	12	0	64	3.2	Agreed
Grand Mean							3.13	Acceptable
Standard Deviation							0.19	
Deviation								

The table above shows the mean responses of the respondents'. They had a fairly positive response on their experiences during teaching practice. The mean is greater than the criterion mean of 2.5. They strongly agreed to the experiences. An average mean of 3.13 shows a high agreement rate on the various items, while a standard deviation of 0.19 reveals a low variability in their responses.

Research Question Two: *What are the experiences of Physics student teachers during their teaching practice with respect to gender?*

Table 2: Group Statistics for the mean responses of Male and female respondents on their Experiences during Teaching Practice

S/N	QUESTION	Weighted mean for male	Weighted mean for female
1	I learnt how to prepare a lesson note effectively.	3.0	3.3
2	The feedback I received during my teaching practice was constructive.	3.2	3.2
3	I was able to overcome stage fright during teaching.	3.2	3.2
4	The teaching resources available during my practice were adequate.	2.7	3.0
5	I encountered positive interactions with students during my teaching practice.	3.0	3.0
6	I faced challenges in maintaining classroom discipline during my teaching practice.	3.1	3.2
7	The support from mentor teachers positively influenced my teaching practice.	3.0	3.2
8	I found it easy to adapt my teaching methods to suit different learning styles.	2.9	3.4
9	I believe my teaching practice helped me develop effective communication skills.	2.3	3.3
10	The overall experience of my teaching practice was rewarding.	3.0	3.2
	Grand Mean	3.06	3.20

Table 3 shows the mean responses of male and female Physics students' teachers experiences during the teaching practice exercise.

S/n	Respondents	sample size	mean
1	Male	13	3.06
2	Female	7	3.20

Null Hypothesis One

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the male and female Physics student teachers responses on their teaching practice experience.

Table 4: t-test statistics results between male and female Physics teachers responses on teaching practice experiences.

	Paired Differences	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower	Upper	t test	df	p-value
Means Difference between male and female	-0.26	0.3062	0.0968	0.4790	0.0409	2.6849	9	0.025**

Footnote: **=Sig at 5%

Using data from table 4 to find the t ratio, we had -2.685 while the p-value was 0.025. Taking into note the fact that the critical point = ± 1.96 (where $\alpha = 0.05$), the value we have (-2.685) is not within the range of the critical point and also, the p-value (0.025) is greater than the α (0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) is not retained. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the male and female Physics student teachers on their responses during teaching practice experience.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

There was a fairly high positive response from the respondents on their experiences during Teaching Practice. This is shown in almost all the items ranging from learning how to prepare a lesson note, overcoming stage fright, to developing communication skills. The Physics Student Teachers who participated in this research had very similar responses which shows that the concept of Teaching Practice is a positive one and should have positive impacts, in line with Oyediji and Oke (2020) & Nghia and Tai (2019), where they stated that experiences gained during teaching practice play a pivotal role in shaping the confidence and effectiveness of Physics Student Teachers in their future roles, while also fostering professional growth and networking opportunities for Physics Student Teachers. However, the null hypothesis is not retained. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the male and female Physics student teachers on their responses towards teaching practice experience. Though a slight difference in their responses which could be liken to the fact that the female are more committed and they prefer the teaching job. These agrees with Cebi and Reisoglu (2020) who mentioned that despite slight differences that may arise from their differences in gender, male and female Physics Student Teachers have similar teaching practice experiences.

CONCLUSION

The paper investigated the experiences of the Physics student teacher during the Teaching practice exercise. These experiences make the Student Teacher become a competent teacher. The experiences gotten by Physics Student teachers during Teaching Practice such as preparing lesson note effectively, receiving constructive criticism, ability to overcome stage fright during teaching, also learning to adapt to teaching methods to suit different learning styles and being able to develop effective communication skills all positive experiences which the students more effective in real world practice. The experiences however, contributed positively to their professional growth and capacity in the teaching field.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Teaching practice exercise should be made mandatory that every students undergo teaching practice twice during the academic session before graduating from the higher institution of learning to enable the students gain confidence.
2. There should be strict supervision on the students during the teaching practice period.

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